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RESEARCHES ON SEMANTIC-FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES OF JAPANESE ADVERTISING

Annotation: *This article focuses on researches about the semantic-functional features of discourses in Japanese advertising. There are also examples and explanations of advertisements in the subway that inform passengers about the importance of exemplary social behaviour and ethics.*

Keywords: *Japanese advertising, discourse, semantic-functional feature*

Advertising discourse can be considered a hybrid type due to its complex form provided by interconnections of social, cultural, historical, and economic nature, which lead to intertextuality and genre mixing, yet its main purpose is to obtain maximum effect with minimum effort.

The term "intertextuality" is used in reference to the relation of one text with other texts (Alfaro 1996). The analysis of language use offers valuable evidence in terms of observing and understanding shifts in cultural values and perceptions of the world. Considering the chameleonic nature of advertising discourse, we propose an interdisciplinary approach taking into account relevant theories in the field of discourse analysis and cultural semiotics.

Its forms of manifestation both differ from and resemble others created in a different cultural and social sphere. Besides the influence of other fields of study and types of discourses, another significant factor, which contributes to the changes in discourse construction, is the influence of global trends, which promise to bring a prestigious aura.

Thus, in the case of Japanese advertising discourse, the phenomena of adopting and adapting foreign elements played a major role in establishing a new trend, significantly contributing to the image of what is known to be "cool Japan".

Many researchers (Hodge and Kress 1988; Cook 1992, 2002; Fairclough 1989, 1995; Malefyt and Moeran 2003; Tungate 2013) dealing with advertising discourse have approached this subject from a variety of viewpoints (involving marketing, social sciences, linguistics and semiotics, etc.) in search for understanding and explaining the particularities and mechanism of this multimodal discourse. Regardless of the chosen method, the constant element in these studies has been its persuasive, manipulative (not necessarily in a pejorative sense), seductive nature.

Due to the fact that advertising discourse is perhaps the most complex type of discourse, in which intertextuality plays a major role in discourse construction, we consider that an interdisciplinary approach to discourse analysis is in demand. Our study aims to describe the Japanese society based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions in order to

provide an understanding of cultural differences followed by a corpus analysis from a sociolinguistic perspective and to demonstrate that interculturality does not “erase” or disregard traditional values and norms, but, on the contrary, it shows that this particular symbiosis enriches the discourse.

This particular type of advertisement offers significant insight into general perceptions of the world, which are connected to culture and tradition, and these specificities reflect in discourse construction. Thus, in the case of Japanese manner or etiquette adverts regarding commuter behaviour, we will explore and analyse the constituent signs in relation to *kawaii* aesthetics reflected in both visual signs and text. Starting from the hypothesis that advertising discourse is constructed in order to persuade the receiver and that objective can be achieved only if there is a common, familiar cultural and social background involved, we will focus on interpreting the underlying meanings in order to see how foreign elements contribute to the changes in Japanese discourse construction .

We will conduct a social semiotic analysis on three non-commercial adverts displayed on trains and subway walls after 2000. Starting from the considerations that a thorough study on advertising discourse needs to interconnect text and context in order to create an integrative research model, we will construct our research by taking into account that words are not to be regarded as isolated elements but as components of the global meaning.

By following Hodge and Kress's (1988) model of analysis, our aim is to reveal the mechanism through which foreign elements enrich Japanese advertising discourse. Having as a starting point Moeran's statement: “Europe is seen by the Japanese as a repository of ‘high culture’, and thus of cultural ‘depth’” (2003: 106) and that “orientalist and occidentalist images become focal points in a global stylistic continuity and tend thus to be the same, whether they are produced in Japan, Europe or the United States. They both integrate the other and are integrated in the other” (Malefyt and Moeran 2003: 107; emphasis in the original), we shall continue this idea by analysing a series of printed adverts regarding commuters' etiquette.

As Yano (2013: 16) presents it, the strategy that accelerated the process of integration and high-speed adaptation (we would add) of foreign trends in Japanese advertising discourse and assured its success overseas was due to the concept of *mukokuseki* ‘lack of nationality’ or, more simplified, erasure of Asian origins.

It seems that the non-nationalistic appeal is responsible for the popularity of the characters created in this spirit (Iwabuchi 2002: 33). As Iwabuchi (2002) states, the term seems to be used in two ways: “to suggest the mixing of elements of multiple cultural origins and to imply the erasure of visible ethnic and cultural characteristics” (Iwabuchi 2002: 71). For example, the Japanese anime ‘animation’ is often referred to as “*mukokuseki* visual culture”, and we consider that this idea can be extrapolated and applied to media as well because in most cases Japanese advertising discourse implies hybrid language use and visuals .

The best-known example in this sense is Hello Kitty, the character that, according to its constructed background, is a British “citizen” who can be stated to be responsible for

"cute globalization" (Yano 2013). Further elaborating on this idea, we shall conduct an analysis on a selected corpora of relevant printed advertisements in order to elaborate the importance of kawaii in the two-way process: firstly, that of adapting foreign elements in discourse construction according to Japanese principles and values (Japanization) and, secondly, that of integration of Japanese products and values via mukokuseki . We argue that the appeal to gairaigo, wasei-eigo and the extensive use of onomatopoeia, metaphors, and puns in Japanese advertisements are highly influenced by global trends mainly because of the prestige they seem to bring.

In several studies (Miller 1998, Hogan 2003, Hatanaka and Pannel 2016), it has been argued that the tendency of using non-traditional Japanese words in favour of borrowed words and/or pseudo-Anglicism is due to their capacity to express the inexpressible, to convey Western qualities, to refer to and bear "different shades of meaning and stylistic value allowing for a greater range of expression" (Rebuck 2002: 55). This tendency of using Japanese wago, Chinese origin kango, and borrowed words has shaped advertising discourse construction. Thus, from the selected adverts, we will list and explain the purpose and effects resulted from choosing one word over another in our attempt to describe the phenomena.

This study will probably benefit researchers who are interested in advertising discourse analysis from a linguistic and cultural semiotics perspective, considering that research on media discourse has increased and the outcomes can offer valuable insight into cultural transfers especially in the globalized world in which "cultural diversity and translation problems discourage standardization of advertising message" (Lazovic 2012: 42)

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